

NOTES

TABLE I

Compound	Colour	Melting (m), decomposition (d) or transition (t) temperature	Found%				Calcd.%			
			C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M
Li1N2N.Sa1A	Dark brown	215-220°d	63.51	3.81	4.09	—	64.35	3.79	4.42	—
Na1N2N.Sa1A	Dark brown	198-200°d	60.80	2.91	3.88	6.80	61.26	3.60	4.20	6.91
K1N2N.Sa1A	Yellowish green	170°t, 180°d	58.29	3.40	3.88	11.00	58.45	3.44	4.01	11.18
Li8HQ.Sa1A	Canary yellow	117-120°m	65.72	4.00	4.31	—	66.44	4.15	4.84	—
Na8HQ.Sa1A	Yellow	105-110°m	62.60	3.90	4.45	7.50	62.95	3.93	4.59	7.54
K8HQ.Sa1A	Yellow	105-110°m	58.16	3.25	4.81	12.00	59.81	3.74	4.36	12.15
Li1N2N.AcSa1A	Dark brown	235-240°d	63.39	3.88	4.11	—	63.51	3.90	3.90	—
Na1N2N.AcSa1A	Greenish brown	210°d	60.71	3.68	3.51	6.05	60.80	3.73	3.73	6.13
K1N2N.AcSa1A	Greenish brown	190°d	59.21	3.70	3.98	9.65	58.31	3.58	3.58	9.97
Li8HQ.AcSa1A	Pale Yellow	146-150°d	66.30	3.10	4.19	—	65.26	4.23	4.23	—
K8HQ.AcSa1A	Cream	160° mcd	59.51	3.28	3.71	10.65	59.50	3.86	3.86	10.74
Li1N2N.2H3NA	Brown	195-200°d	69.12	3.21	3.42	—	68.66	3.82	3.82	—
Na1N2N.2H3NA	Brown	155-160°d	65.60	3.54	3.53	5.95	65.80	3.66	3.66	6.01
K1N2N.2H3NA	Yellowish green	180°d	62.91	3.72	3.14	9.52	63.16	3.51	3.51	9.77
Li8HQ.2H3NA	Light brown	230-235°d	70.21	4.30	3.81	—	70.80	4.13	4.13	—
Na8HQ.2H3NA	Yellow	150-155°d	67.01	3.56	3.77	6.35	67.61	3.94	3.94	6.48
K8HQ.2H3NA	Yellow	150°d	64.51	3.52	3.71	10.40	64.69	3.77	3.77	10.51

1N2N=1-nitroso-2-naphthol; 8HQ=8-hydroxyquinoline; Sa1A=salicylic acid; AcSa1A=acetyl salicylic acid and 2H3NA=2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid.

TABLE 2—SELECTED ABSORPTION BANDS IN DIFFERENT REGIONS (IN cm^{-1})

	O—H/O...H—O		O...H—O/O...H—N				O...H—O		
1N2N		3300br		3055				1640(N=O)	
Sa1A		3240(O—H)					1660(C=O)		1483
Li1N2N.Sa1A		3280					1630	1600	
Na1N2N.Sa1A	3400		2300	1880	1680	1670	1640	1620	
K1N2N.Sa1A	3400	3360	2300br	1920	1690	1675	1650	1615	
8HQ		3440(OH)							1580(C=N)
Li8HQ.Sa1A			3100-3050				1650	1630br	1600 1560
Na8HQ.Sa1A			3100-3050	2500-2400			1645	1625	1595
K8HQ.Sa1A			3100-3000	2500-2450	1800		1635		1600
AcSa1A		3300-3100br		2500-2400	1750	1680	1650sh		1600
Li1N2N.AcSa1A		3270			1890		1640(N=O)		1615 1520
Na1N2N.AcSa1A			3030	2500	1880-60		1660	1650sh	1640 1615 1520
K1N2N.AcSa1A	3420	3350br		2250br	1910	1695	1660br	1645	1615 1520
Li8HQ.AcSa1A		3300		2550-2500			1660		1615 1560
2H3NA		3265				1680sh	1660	1620	1590 1500
Li1N2N.2H3NA		3250						1630	
Na1N2N.2H3NA		3250	3030	2550-2500	1900		1645	1635	1610 1585 1500
K1N2N.2H3NA	3420	3380		2300br	1820br		1658	1650	1630 1580 1500
Li8HQ.2H3NA		3300-3200							1600 1585 1500
Na8HQ.2H3NA				2500	1850-1800			1615	1595 1585 1570
K8HQ.2H3NA			3100-3000	2550-2500	1800			1630	1595 1500

References

1. A. K. BANERJEE, A. J. LAYTON, R. S. NYHOLM and MARRY R. TRUTER, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 292.
2. A. K. BANERJEE, DHARM PRAKASH and S. K. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 691.
3. A. K. BANERJEE, DHARM PRAKASH and S. K. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 458, 465 and 462.
4. A. K. BANERJEE, P. KAJARIWAL and S. K. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 705.
5. R. C. LORD and R. E. MERRYFIELD, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1953, 21, 166.

Studies on the Kinetics of Production of Charge Carriers in $\text{CuCl} - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ System*

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PURE cuprous chloride is a white crystalline material having zinc blende lattice but usually has a yellowish greenish appearance as a result of oxidation of cuprous chloride by air. The

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yellow greenish material is always found to contain considerable amount of basic oxy chloride¹. Oxidation of cuprous chloride by Cl₂ gas has been extensively studied by Harrison and Ng², the reaction product being anhydrous defective CuCl_x where x is from 1 to 1.9. The oxidation has been found to increase the concentration of positive holes³. The oxidation of CuCl pellet by moisture, CuCl being in equilibrium with metallic copper as electrode, has been found to produce short circuit current as reported earlier^{3,4}. We report here the correlation of the short circuit current to the kinetics of production of charge carrier during the reaction.

Experimental

Cuprous chloride AR, B. D. H., was purified and pellets were prepared as earlier⁴. The pellets were annealed at 100° for nearly 3 hrs to remove traces of moisture and then charged between preweighed copper and platinum disc electrodes giving the configuration Cu/CuCl/Pt. The EMF and the resistance of the cell were measured with the help of H.P. Electrometer Model 412 A and Beckmann Conductivity bridge Model RC-18 A. Low and high short circuit currents were measured with ammeters model 474 Kaycee and Weston 301 respectively. The cell was then introduced into a glass chamber where water vapour was allowed to react with CuCl. Short circuit current was measured at regular intervals of time. To observe the effect of different electrode materials on the behaviour of the cell, copper was replaced by a silver electrode and in a separate trial a symmetrical cell Cu/CuCl/Cu was also used.

Results and Discussion

Pellets of cuprous chloride were charged in three distinct cell assemblies, type I, type II and type III corresponding to Cu/CuCl/Pt, Ag/CuCl/Pt and Cu/CuCl/Cu respectively. Each assembly was found to behave as a cell giving short circuit current and the behaviour of the cells is distinguishable from one another as described below :

Type I—The cell was studied first at room temperature and then the measurements were made at upto 55°. At room temperatures, at the onset of moisture adsorption by the pellet the current started rising at the rate of 0.80 mA cm⁻² m mole⁻¹ H₂O ; Fig. 1 (solid circle). The rise in current continued for about 3 hrs during which the total water adsorbed was 1 m mole. Thereafter the current stabilised giving a maximum value of 0.8 mA cm⁻² and remained constant for several hrs.

Type II—In this case the copper electrode was replaced by a silver electrode of identical dimensions. The rise of current was at the rate of 0.30 mA cm⁻² m mole⁻¹ which is about 37% of the value in type I. The rise in current continued for 3 hrs as in the case of type I. Thereafter, the current started decreasing and finally became constant at

Fig. 1. Data showing short circuit current density vs millimoles of H₂O adsorbed ; cell Cu/CuCl/Pt and Ag/CuCl/Pt.

approximately 0.15 mA cm⁻² in 3 hrs ; Fig. 1 (open circle). The behaviour of type II was thus in contrast with that observed in type I.

Type III—The behaviour of this symmetrical cell, where both the electrodes were copper, was much different from either of the other two. In this case the current rose at the rate of 0.067 mA cm⁻² m mole⁻¹ only for an hour reaching a maximum of 45 μA cm⁻² and thereafter it decayed to almost zero within 5 hrs.

Cuprous chloride is a *p*-type material⁵⁻¹² below ~130° and *p* type conductivity results due to its non-stoichiometric nature (chlorine excess). Now let us see how the chemical reaction occurring in presence of moisture with CuCl can influence the positive hole concentration in this material (the oxidation of CuCl by Cl₂ has been found to enhance the positive holes concentration enormously⁹). The following chemical reaction appears to take place between CuCl pellet and H₂O and is considered for the discussion of our results.

From the stoichiometry of the above reaction and neglecting Cu(OH)₂ since it will not remain as a part of CuCl-matrix, each molecule of H₂O reacted amounts to the production of one Cu⁺⁺ in the CuCl matrix. Each Cu⁺⁺ in CuCl is capable of acting as a positive hole. Consequently, the formation of each Cu⁺⁺ in CuCl could be considered as if a positive hole capable of transporting positive charge has been produced. Thus, as an approximation, the experimentally observed current density could be taken as proportional to the concentration of charge carriers which are produced in this reaction and diffuse due to a concentration gradient. Hence the general kinetic expression for the production of charge carriers may be written as

$$\frac{dc}{dt} = k (\text{moles of H}_2\text{O reacted})^n \dots (2)$$

where dc/dt is the rate of production of charge carriers, k is the rate constant and n is the order

of such reaction. Since the observed current density is considered to be proportional to the rate of production of charge carriers, the logarithmic plot of current density vs m mole of H_2O should yield a straight line with $\log_{10} k$ as an intercept and n as a slope of the line.

In order to test the validity of the above approximation for the kinetic law the data of all the three types of cell have been utilised. For type I, a plot of $\log_{10} I_d$ vs \log_{10} m moles of H_2O (where I_d is the current density) has been shown in Fig. 2. The straight line suggests that the charge carrier generation in the system is of a first order at each temperature. This behaviour is observed even at higher temperatures. The rate

Fig. 2. Logarithmic plot of I_d vs H_2O adsorbed at different temperature; cell Cu/CuCl/Pt.

constants at four different temperatures were estimated from the intercepts.

Similar data were plotted for type II and type III cells and showed that the reaction in each case obeys first order kinetics. This, however, is not true at higher H_2O concentration.

Fig. 3. Arrhenius plot of rate constant.

Finally, the Arrhenius plot of the type I data appears to be significantly informative. The Arrhenius plot of rate constant has been shown in Fig. 3 and this plot shows an activation energy of 0.34 eV. This activation energy favours the positive hole charge transport in carrying the current as proposed here.

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References

1. J. R. PARTINGTON, "A Text Book of Inorganic Chemistry", Macmillan & Co. Ltd. 1930, 796.
2. L. G. HARRISON and C. F. NG., *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1971, **67**, 1810.
3. M. PRASAD and J. K. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, (communicated).
4. M. PRASAD and J. K. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 395.
5. C. TURANDT, *Handbook der Experimental Physics*, 1932, **12**, 385.
6. C. WAGNER and J. B. WAGNER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, **26**, 1597.
7. Y. W. HSUEH and R. W. CHRISTY, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, **39**, 3519.
8. R. S. BRADLEY, D. C. MUNRO and P. N. SPENCER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1969, **65**, 1912.
9. M. PRASAD, Ph.D. Thesis, Univ. of British Columbia, 1973.
10. L. G. HARRISON and M. PRASAD, *Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans I*, 1974, **70**, 471.
11. T. MATSUI and J. B. WAGNER, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1977, **124**, 610.
12. T. MATSUI and J. B. WAGNER, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1977, **124**, 941.

Polarographic Behaviour of Ga(III), In(III) and Ge(IV) in Aqueous Mixtures of Organic Solvents

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THOUGH the polarographic behaviour of various inorganic depolarizers in aqueous mixtures of organic solvents has been studied¹⁻¹⁶, studies on polarographic behaviour of Ga(III), In(III) and Ge(IV) in aqueous mixtures of organic solvents are still lacking. With this in view a polarographic study of the influence of aqueous mixtures of methanol, ethanol, acetone, acetonitrile and dimethylformamide on the kinetics of electrode reactions of these depolarizers has been undertaken. The influence of increasing concentrations of organic solvents on the electrode reactions of the depolarizers has been explained in terms of the values of kinetic parameters αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ calculated by Koutacky's method¹⁸⁻²¹.